

D3.1 Preliminary report on inconsistencies, interoperability methods and alignment of observations and models

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List of abbreviations

AMRIT	Advance Marine Infrastructures Together
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
API	Application Programming Interface
AQUARIUS	Aqua Research Infrastructure Services for the health and protection of our unique, oceans, seas and freshwater ecosystems (Horizon Europe project)
BMBF-ITMS	Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (now Bundesministerium für Forschung, Technologie und Raumfahrt) Integriertes Treibhausgas-Monitoringsystem für Deutschland - Coastal Greenhouse gas Emissions
CoastGEM	
CDOM	Coloured/Chromophoric Dissolved Organic Matter
Chl	Chlorophyll
CMEMS GLO/IBI L4	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service Global/Iberia-Biscay-Ireland Level 4 Product
COINS	Copernicus Observations In-situ Networking and Sustainability
DOC	Dissolved Organic Carbon
DOM	Dissolved Organic Matter
DOORS	Horizon 2020 project 'Developing Optimal and Open Research Support' for the Black Sea'
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EO	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
EU	European Union

FAIR	findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable
FDOM	Fluorescent Dissolved Organic Matter
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HF	High Frequency
HPLC	High Performance Liquid Chromatography
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
IOP	Inherent Optical Property
JERICO	Joint European Research Infrastructure for the Coastal Ocean
JPI Oceans	Joint Programming Initiative Healthy and Productive Seas and Oceans
LIL	LandSeaLot Integration Lab
LSI	Land-Sea Interface
MOHID	MOHID water modelling system
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MX.Y	Milestone X.Y
NO ₃	Nitrate
O ₂	Oxygen
OSPAR	Oslo and Paris Conventions
RI ILICO	French national research infrastructure for coastal observation
SEB LIL	Seine Estuary and Bay LandSeaLot Integration Lab
SI	International System of Units
SOCAT	The Surface Ocean CO ₂ Atlas
SOOP	Shaping an Ocean of Opportunity
SPM	Suspended Particulate Matter
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
SWOT	Surface Water and Ocean Topography
TX.Y	Task X.Y
WP	Work Package
WSRE LIL	Wadden Sea Rhine Elbe LandSeaLot Integration Lab

1. Executive Summary

The LandSeaLot project aims to improve the observation and thus inform management of the Land-Sea Interface (LSI) the dynamic zone where terrestrial, riverine, and marine systems interact. This area is critical for economic activities, biodiversity, and climate resilience but is increasingly vulnerable to environmental stressors such as climate extremes and pollution. In support of the EU Green Deal and Blue Economy goals, LandSeaLot seeks to enhance environmental observation and inform sustainable management through an integrated observation framework.

Deliverable D3.1, developed under Work Package 3 (WP3), lays the groundwork for improving interoperability between *in-situ*, Earth Observation (EO), and model-based environmental data. D3.1 identifies key inconsistencies, data gaps, and integration challenges at the LSI and outlines an approach for harmonizing observation and modelling efforts. This includes a focus on seven priority parameters – (water) temperature, dissolved oxygen, turbidity/SPM, Chl, DOC/CDOM, NO₃, *in-situ* reflectance – and the selection of test cases for data interoperability workflows across nine LandSeaLot Integration Labs (LILs) throughout Europe.

Key activities of WP3 described in this deliverable include:

- Identifying interoperability issues between observation systems and ways to address them through dedicated test cases.
- Engaging domain experts through surveys, questionnaires, and workshops to prioritize parameters and identify integration obstacles.
- Defining workflows for data integration across domains (*in-situ*, EO, modelling) and across LILs.
- Proposing steps toward a Digital Twin of the LSI area – a real-time, interactive platform that models environmental conditions using harmonized data streams and predictive models.

Preliminary findings show significant challenges for FAIR data, particularly:

- Variability in observation methods and instruments.
- Fragmentation of data repositories and standards.
- Limited interoperability between communities (*in-situ*, EO, modelling).
- Gaps in metadata, calibration, and validation processes.

D3.1 proposes improved standardization of methods and metadata, and development of a common EU-based data repository for LSI data. These elements are essential for building a Digital Twin that enables scenario planning, real-time feedback, and decision support tools for sustainable LSI management.

D3.1 sets the stage for further developments in D3.2 “Final report on inconsistencies, interoperability methods and alignment of observations and models” and D3.3 “Roadmap for integrating observations and models at the land-sea interface”, guiding the European effort to transform LSI observation through integrated, digital, and stakeholder-informed approaches.

2. Introduction

2.1. Role of this deliverable in the context LandSeaLot

LandSeaLot is a European project that brings together diverse expertise to better understand and inform management of the Land-Sea Interface (LSI), the dynamic zone where land, rivers and ocean meet. These areas support major economic activities such as fisheries, aquaculture, tourism, energy and shipping and consequently contribute significantly to national GDPs. At the same time, these exchange environments represent hotspots for biodiversity and are exceptionally vulnerable to climate extremes acting within the catchment (floods and droughts) and in the adjacent marine environment (marine heat waves, storm surges and sea level rise, and the impact of flood/droughts on the coast), as well as pollution events. These stressors act both in isolation and in combination, contributing significant risks to the sustainability of these environments along the LSI, the ecosystems they support, and the communities and regional and national economies. Despite these threats, and conflicting interests, the coastal regions and shelf seas are expected to contribute significantly to fulfilling the ambition of securing six times more food and 40 times more energy from the sea, as stated by world leaders at the UN Ocean Conference in Lisbon in June 2022.

Figure 1: LandSeaLot Integration Labs (LILs).

LandSeaLot aims to help balance these competing demands by improving how we observe the coastal environment. The project builds on and connects existing observation efforts, including *in-situ* observation, satellite data, modelling tools and citizen science, to create a more integrated picture of coastal systems. This work is being piloted in nine LandSeaLot Integration Labs (LILs, see Figure 1)) across Europe, each focused on local challenges and

engaging local stakeholders. Each LIL explores how observation strategies can support sustainable development, inform policy and management and strengthen community engagement. Insights from these LILs will help shape a shared European approach to observing the LSI area.

New tools are urgently required to assess the efficacy of deploying new infrastructure to support the sustainable growth in blue economy, the green deal and climate adaptation interventions at the land-sea interface area. These tools must support:

- i. decision making including the optimal siting and deployment of strategic assets and interventions.
- ii. management and control of these interventions to optimize their deployment and benefit to society.
- iii. assess their short- and longer-term impacts and benefits in the face of a changing environment.
- iv. de-risk investment and maximize benefits realization, whilst ensure sustainability, equity in service delivery and resolving competing demands.

The observational framework coupled with the modelling outputs presented by LandSeaLot provide the ‘stepping stones’ for the development of dedicated digital twins of the land-sea interface area. We now have access to large volumes of new, rich and highly heterogeneous data and tools and approaches that can transform our systems understanding of these complex environments. However, these data are not available everywhere and LandSeaLot starts by working in the LILs that have some of the best observational systems in place and can showcase suggested optimal approaches proposed in LandSeaLot. LandSeaLot works in support of the Digital Twin for the Land Sea Interface that will comprise of a digital platform that enables real time visualization and interaction with a digital replica of the Land-Sea-Interface, that updates and learns from real time and near real time data flows, supported by archived data, and that allows design solutions to be embedded. The Digital Twin provides systems understanding of the past, present and future allowing scenarios to be explored and provides real feedback with embedded uncertainties to support decision making and control.

WP3 addresses these challenges. Working with researchers and the practitioner and stakeholder communities at the land-sea interface area, WP3 is addressing inconsistencies, both spatial and temporal, in the observation, quality and availability of environmental data. The lack of interoperability methods and alignment of observations and models, poses considerable barriers to the efficient use of available data towards the planning of efficient observation strategies.

WP3’s task is to identify gaps, similarities and complementarities especially in current *in-situ* observation efforts but also in their relationship with the Earth Observation (EO) and modelling communities. The insights gained, will enable LandSeaLot to provide recommendations and integration, assimilation and fusion frameworks for improved observations and further harmonization between the *in-situ*, EO and modelling data generators. The main goal of this Deliverable is to document the LandSeaLot efforts to

prepare and test the approach to find and address these issues, so that the approach can then be used more widely in preparation for the final version of this Deliverable (D3.2, M34).

Improving interoperability and addressing data gaps are essential steps toward enabling more consistent monitoring and increase systems understanding across the LILs, whilst also providing the robust foundation to develop digital twins of the land-sea interface area. Digital twins of the land–sea interface rely on the seamless integration of different data sources, including real-time observations and model outputs, to provide accurate, dynamic representations of coastal systems. Achieving this integration requires consistent, harmonized data streams across different domains, platforms and spatial scales by addressing observational inconsistencies and strengthening the links between *in-situ*, satellite and modelling communities. The knowledge exchange, integration frameworks and best practices developed and tested through the LILs, through WP3 and as outlined in the Roadmap (D3.3) will support the creation of digital twins that can support the next generation of European coastal management.

2.2. Aims of the deliverable

This deliverable provides first recommendations for addressing interoperability issues between observation (both, *in-situ* and EO) and model communities along the land-sea interface area, by providing an approach for identifying inconsistencies, gaps and overlaps, which include:

- 1) Identifying a set of parameters essential for observation and models to study LSI areas.
- 2) Inquiring experts to identify major inconsistencies and needs for addressing interoperability challenges.
- 3) Identifying test cases in LILs, where the workflow on addressing these inconsistencies and challenges is articulated and tested to resolve them.
- 4) Laying the groundwork for Task 3.4, i.e. working towards creation of a roadmap and best practices in integrating observations and models; and
- 5) Identifying needs and future steps to be undertaken within the LILs towards the development of digital twins of LSI areas. This aims to set the stage for producing a roadmap towards a Digital Twin.

3. Summary of information sources

This deliverable builds on various information sources which include expert knowledge from the authors and the LandSeaLot expert community, survey and questionnaire data and outcomes from workshops hosted in the first one and a half year of the LandSeaLot project. The sources of information used, are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Sources of information used in this deliverable. Details are described in sections 4 and 5 of this Deliverable.

Information source	Description
Questionnaire 1: Priority Variables Online Questionnaire (Oct 2014)	LandSeaLot WP3 members and <i>in-situ</i> experts were invited to complete an online questionnaire (https://forms.gle/FhP4tjEKffuwPaE9), the members were queried to indicate five parameters that are most relevant to their work AND best suited as examples for integrating observations.
<i>In-situ</i> Parameters Workshop (12 Nov 2024)	Workshop hosted by HEREON
Integration Workshop LandSeaLot Week 2025 (Jan 2025, Milestone 8)	In-person workshop with representatives from all LILs and all work packages. Full findings are documented in Milestone 8.
Questionnaire 2: Online questionnaire for inconsistencies, interoperability methods and alignment of observations and models	Members of WP3 were invited to fill in a questionnaire (https://forms.gle/vL7gebBRuNPZbab2A) to collect expert experience on inconsistencies, interoperability methods and alignment of observations and models. They were asked to give answers referring to one of the defined focus parameters.
Monthly WP3 meetings	Regular online meetings of WP3 members to share updates of work within T3.1, T3.2 and T3.3 and discuss and refine outcomes of the other information sources in this table.
LandSeaLot Milestone 7 (Nov 2024)	First recommendation on interoperability of <i>in-situ</i> observation systems - Minutes of Meeting with land-sea <i>in-situ</i> community.

4. Priority variables selection within and across LILs (mapping inconsistencies, interoperability methods and alignment of observations and models)

A tiered approach was used to address the LandSeaLot expert community. This approach is described in the next sections.

4.1. Methods of priority parameters selection

The creation of a parameter short list was necessary for WP3 to focus efforts in identifying overlaps and complementariness of *in-situ* capabilities across LILs, including benchmarking of *in-situ* observation practises across LILs and identifying existing best practises or where new ones need to be developed (Task 3.1). Efforts were undertaken to determine the level of integration of *in-situ* parameters, to prioritize parameters likely to be integrated with other data across LILs.

WP3 identified experts of *in-situ* observations within the LandSeaLot consortium (Table 2) using the LandSeaLot partner expertise matrix generated by WP2. The members of the workgroup were given the opportunity to suggest additional experts outside of LandSeaLot where needed. It was agreed upon to develop a workflow using *in-situ* observations as well as environmental observational parameters commonly measured across all domains to improve interoperability of data along the land-sea-interface. Overall, 38 *in-situ* experts were identified from the LandSeaLot expertise matrix and suggested by the Task 3.1 workgroup.

Table 2: List of *in-situ* experts within the LandSeaLot consortium including their key expertise/s (modified from table 1 in LandSeaLot Milestone 7).

Institution	<i>in-situ</i> expertise	Number of experts	present at workshop
+ATL	Heatwaves, EO ground truthing, Coastal erosion	3	1
CNR	Acidification	1	0
Covartec	Nutrients, Coastal erosion, Observing technologies development	1	1
GeoEcoMar	Coastal erosion, River bank erosion, Storm surges, Floods, Nutrients, Plastics	4	1
ETT	Low-cost observation technology	3	0
HCMR	Nutrients, Carbon fluxes & stocks, Acidification, Salinization, Heatwaves, Biodiversity	4	0
Hereon	Contaminants (POPs & heavy metals), Plastics, Nutrients, Carbon fluxes & stocks, Acidification, Heatwaves, Floods, Low-cost observation technology, Observing technologies development	3	2
Ifremer	Nutrients, Coastal erosion, Biodiversity, River bank erosion, Salinization, Heatwaves, Floods, Observing technologies development	10	2

Norce	Carbon fluxes & stocks, Acidification, Salinization, Heatwaves	1	0
SMHI	Carbon fluxes & stocks, Low-cost observation technology, Observing technologies development, Storm surges	3	1
Syke	Nutrients, Pollution	1	0
USTIR	Contaminants (POPs & heavy metals), Nutrients, Low-cost observation technology, Plastics, Coastal erosion, River bank erosion, Land erosion, Salinization	3	1

LandSeaLot WP3 members and *in-situ* experts were invited in 2024 to complete an online questionnaire (<https://forms.gle/FhP4tjEKffwuwPaE9>), requiring them to suggest priority, *in-situ* variables. LandSeaLot *in-situ* experts were invited to an online workshop on 12 November 2024. Eight members from the *in-situ* expert list participated in the virtual workshop. All others were given the opportunity to contribute to the outcome via an online form. Experts in variables other than the identified focus parameters were also asked to join to advise whether the discussed points were applicable to other parameters as well. During the meeting, each participant introduced his/her background, and the group was asked to share their experience with common challenges concerning data availability, access, and interoperability, as well as to discuss any potential recommended solutions to these issues. Results and notes were collected in a shared online document, which was distributed by email to all invitees after the workshop, asking them to contribute with additional input. The parameter shortlist was presented to the wider LandSeaLot consortium during the LandSeaLot week in Lisbon in January 2025. A discussion there consolidated the list of priority (*in-situ*) variables (MS8).

A second questionnaire (<https://forms.gle/6HHpuL9uMDeStekX7>) was prepared to address the issues of D3.1 and D3.2, namely:

- inconsistencies
- interoperability methods
- alignment of observations and models

This questionnaire was distributed on 9 April 2025 to the LandSeaLot experts, first to assess its suitability to generate actionable information on the listed issues. Following their assessment, the questionnaire will be updated and distributed more widely to generate information for the final version of this Deliverable (D3.2, M34).

4.2. List of priority parameters

There was consensus that a nutrient related parameter should be added, but that there is currently no good dataset from nutrient sensors and no cost-efficient sensors exist yet for nutrient observations. Nevertheless, the addition of nutrient parameters is needed to ensure that the list contains enough parameters so that at least one societal challenge (see Figure 1, top right corner for these challenges) is addressed in each LSL.

As a result of the integration workshop and surveys, the final list of priority parameters agreed upon is:

- (water) temperature
- dissolved oxygen
- turbidity/SPM
- Chl
- DOC/CDOM
- NO₃
- *In-situ* reflectance

This priority parameter list ensures a minimum number of parameters required for each LIL to address at least one test case relevant to the LIL’s societal challenges. It is important to note that a focus on these parameters does not mean to suggest that other parameters should, or will not be examined in LandSeaLot. On the contrary, these priority parameters provide the possibility to develop data integration/interoperability workflows that will be tested, adjusted and applied to other essential variables. The latter include salinity, nutrients (other than NO₃), pH and more.

Water level and the derived variable of discharge from rivers were discussed as potential valuable, additional base parameters for the LandSeaLot communities. However, there is already a mature effort underway to produce an interoperable data set/base for water level in EMODnet. Coastal bathymetry was also discussed in connection with sediment transport and coastal erosion. Bathymetry will not directly be included in the priority parameter list because it is not frequently and repeatedly measured in most areas, and in some areas its measurement may be subject to jurisdictional restrictions. It is, however, recommended to regard water level, discharge and bathymetry as prerequisite parameters for the study of most societal challenges within the LILs (e.g., carbon fluxes and budgets, nutrient-driven eutrophication, floods, coastal erosion and estuarine morphodynamics). Thus, as a result from the discussions, surveys and workshops within WP3, it is regarded important to consider them when producing interoperability guidelines. The same is recommended for relevant meteorological parameters (e.g., wind and air temperature).

The identified priority parameters can be linked to the “LandSeaLot thematic groups” established under WP5 as described in Table 3.

Table 3: Thematic groups identified in WP5, where the selected priority parameters will be tested.

LandSeaLot Thematic group	Priority parameter(s)
Carbon fluxes	DOC/CDOM (SPM/turbidity where a relationship with POC can be shown)
Floods and sea water levels	Water level/discharge & bathymetry
Heatwaves	(water) temperature
Coastal erosion and estuarine morphodynamics	turbidity/SPM
Plastics	NA
Nutrients	NO ₃ (include chlorophyll if focus is on eutrophication)

5. Observational challenges specific to the Land Sea Interface

This chapter builds primarily on responses from the second questionnaire and expert knowledge of WP3. At the time of writing, the second questionnaire had eleven responses from five LILs representing the coastal ocean (land side; 50%), coastal ocean (sea side; 25%) and estuary (25%).

5.1. Challenges identified from *in-situ* point of view

Issues with data availability (i.e., gaps), access, and interoperability were not only obvious between the river, estuary, coastal and sea domains of the land-sea-interface, but also exist within each of these domains. For instance, while methods for observing a given parameter, such as chlorophyll concentration, can vary in rivers *versus* marine waters; within marine waters that parameter or its proxy may be observed by various methods, such as, chlorophyll concentration by spectrophotometry, HPLC, or (as proxy) by fluorescence. This presents a major challenge to data use by researchers and other stakeholders. However, the Task 3.1. work group discussed some existing work that shares the LandSeaLot aim of harmonizing observations and data flow at least in the coastal seas, e.g., European data aggregators and OSPAR. Such large-scale efforts must be surveyed to avoid “reinventing the wheel”.

Table 4: Matrix of *in-situ* observation challenges by observed parameters. This table was created during and after the *in-person* integration workshop and was available for input by all experts listed in Table 1.

	Obvious spatial and temporal gaps	Problems of data access	Issues with data interoperability (e.g. between <i>in-situ</i> and EO)
General	Sensor failure in HF data; Already large providers/aggregators still do not have all the data, e.g., river water levels in EMODnet; Little information on cross-section variability.	Having to go to a website to get to the data for download (rather than programmatically downloading data); Distributed data;	Quality control, some available data cannot confidently be used as-is; <i>In-situ</i> sample data are not always easy to integrate with high-frequency measurements;
(water) temperature	Not many temperature observations in rivers and estuaries (depending on geographic region)	Data gathered by minor players and with different distribution processes	EO data decreases quality when approaching the coastal area. Low resolution of SST; EO measures skin temperature while <i>in-situ</i> measurements are at a variety of depths
salinity	Scarce salinity observations in estuaries (depending on system)	Data gathered by different actors with different distribution processes	Some sensors lack reliability and EO products only useful in large river systems

dissolved oxygen	[no input]	[no input]	[no input]
turbidity/SPM/Chl	Biofouling issues. Sensor ranges. Vertical variability to be better investigated	[no input]	Sample Chl and fluorescence Chl are “not the same”; EO suspended sediment measures the total suspended matter (organic and unorganic); ocean colour EO integrates over the eutrophic zone, sample depths <i>in-situ</i> in certain or several depths; Ocean colour EO integrates of the area of a pixel (depending on sensor) while <i>in-situ</i> measures ml to l water probe.
DOC/CDOM	Data “pairs” for calibration need to be produced, do not readily exist, especially because they need to be location-specific;	[no input]	Separating fluorescence from Chl and CDOM. Try to find a correlation between CDOM, FDOM and DOC sample measurements, methods differ so they “see” slightly different things
Nutrients	[no input]	[no input]	[no input]
Water level	Water level only near ports and not in the estuaries (depending on system)	[no input]	EO altimetry poor in the coastal area

When asked to judge the severity of spatial discrepancy of a parameter from 1 to 5, with 5 being most severe; 30% answered 2, 30% answered 3, 30% answered 4, and 10% answered 5. Identified issues were a general lack of data, different locations for measurements of different parameters, and (yet unresolved) differences between *in-situ* measurement and EO or model data that would allow spatial continuity. Larger imbalances in available coverage were reported in coastal seas than in river or estuarine waters, noted as due to the need of mobile research platforms in coastal seas. Lack of data coverage was particularly notable in small water sub-bodies such as tidal channels and lagoons, as well as sub-surface waters.

5.2. Origin of inconsistencies and lack of interoperability

Inconsistencies in the observation and storage of *in-situ* variables at the land–sea interface have several origins. A list of these variables has been compiled from several core sources:

Deliverable D4.1, the Roadmap of the COPERNICUS Water-ForCE project and the COINS report 'Lake Water Quality *In-Situ* Data Requirements and Availability'. The summary below outlines key causes of inconsistency and provides an important foundation for understanding the challenges within the LandSeaLot context.

From Water-ForCE¹:

- Short-term, project-based funding limits the sustainability and continuity of observation systems.
- Fragmentation across numerous repositories with different structures and objectives.
- Lack of harmonized metadata standards.
- Inconsistent quality control and assurance practices among data providers.
- Barriers to data discovery, including unclear cataloguing and user interfaces.
- Variation in spatial and temporal resolution of data collection.
- Unclear or restrictive data licensing and ownership arrangements.
- Weak incentives for long-term data curation and maintenance.
- Manual, inconsistent data entry processes and lack of standard upload formats.
- Technological limitations in repository infrastructure and storage sustainability.

From the COINS Report²:

- Sampling frequency often too low to match satellite overpass timing.
- *In-situ* sampling locations often differ from EO-relevant sites, especially favouring shorelines.
- Differences in measurement methods and instruments reduce data comparability.
- Limited availability and accessibility of datasets due to embargoes or lack of awareness.
- Insufficient metadata to support data discovery, evaluation and reuse.
- Calibration issues and unknown measurement uncertainties in sensor data.
- Monitoring biases toward eutrophic or impacted sites underrepresent certain lake types.
- Lack of harmonization and coordination across regional and global efforts.
- Technical limitations in sensors, especially for hyperspectral and IOP measurements.
- Data licensing and intellectual property rights prevent open access.
- Disconnect between *in-situ* monitoring communities and EO developers; lack of structures that allow for exchange between the different communities
- Lack of standard operating procedures for coordinated sampling and analysis.

¹ [A Roadmap for the future of Copernicus for Water | Water-ForCE](#)

² [Lake Water Quality In-Situ Data Requirements and Availability | Copernicus In Situ](#)

5.3. Interoperability and integration of *in-situ* observations across the Land Sea Interface

Interoperability and integration of different data types and communities can pose challenges and opportunities. LandSeaLot WP3 considers primarily the integration of data from well-established and planned *in-situ* (T3.1) and earth observation (T3.2) approaches, but LandSeaLot also sees the need to integrate the emerging low-cost and citizen science approaches. A separate challenge is the integration of observations of these data sources with operational models within the LILs. Data sources considered in this context comprise:

- a. *In-situ* samples and autonomous measurements.
- b. Remote sensing, especially EO.
- c. Models.
- d. Citizen science, and
- e. Low-cost sensors.

All combinations of these data sources will be tested in terms of data integration. In WP6 the river data, low-cost sensor and citizen science data will receive specific attention to improve the FAIRness of the data from the acquisition up to data sharing (metadata, data format, deployment metadata, etc.)

Results from the second questionnaire show that one third of the respondents reported that none (18%) or little (18%) of the already available data can readily be integrated with other data. Good examples of integration are sparse and appear to require considerable prior effort by other groups such as data providers and those defining standard protocols. Challenges to integration are common and will be discussed in more detail in the final version of this Deliverable (D3.2). However, half of the respondents work in multiple efforts to overcome lack of interoperability and list several projects and initiatives (other than LandSeaLot) tackling this challenge. These projects and initiatives include:

- AMRIT <https://www.amritproject.eu/>
- JPI Oceans (for carbon reference materials)
- RI ILICO - French national research infrastructure for coastal observation
- BMBF-ITMS CoastGEM
- JERICO
- SOCAT database / ICOS
- Several projects related to Digital Twins

Similarly, while most of respondents interact with the EO community, this mostly entails providing *in-situ* data for the improvement of EO products, rather than the use of such products by observational researchers.

Most (63%) respondents provide *in-situ* data to modelers in several formats, and state that the cooperation generally works well on a researcher level. However, only a quarter of the respondents state that their *in-situ* (field) work is informed by model insights.

5.4. Interoperability and integration of *in-situ* observations with EO data

Interoperability between the *in-situ* and EO communities is discussed in more detail in T3.1 and T3.2. For the aspect of interoperability between *in-situ* data and EO data, a differentiation is done between fiducial reference data for calibration and validation of ocean colour EO data and fit-for-purpose data that are gained from *in-situ* data not specifically measured to be compared to EO data. For example, the first case (fiducial reference data) is currently addressed within the FRM4SOC project (ESA funded) that works towards a standardization of ground-based measurements of ocean colour parameters traceable to SI standards. This will enable the closest possible link between *in-situ* and EO based measurements (Banks *et al.* 2020³). On the other hand, the fit-for-purpose data often come from diverse sources such as research projects or monitoring programmes, which come with the above-described limitations (missing or inconsistent metadata, different measurement standards, accessibility, awareness: see section 5.2). Although these limitations are known, the data are often used for validation of EO data. And despite these limitations, *in-situ* data and EO data are used (and need to be used) to describe and understand processes within the LSI.

When comparing *in-situ* and EO observation, it always needs to be taken into account that a small amount of water (water sample) is compared to an integral of a pixel or a macropixel and over depths. The depth is depending here on the clarity of the water. In validation activities, *in-situ* data below 2m depths are often not regarded.

Because EO derived products can be diverse in terms of processing steps applied, units, formats, resolutions; not all products within the EO world are immediately interoperable. This is addressed by a group defining CEOS ARD (<https://ceos.org/ard/>) standards (ARD = Analysis Ready data). The derived EO products need to be documented, and fulfilling standards and certain processing steps is mandatory to be qualified as CEOS ARD product. This enables users to transfer EO derived products to other formats or units. Interoperability of *in-situ*, remote sensing and citizen science data with physics-based and/or data-driven models is challenging for a number of reasons:

- Several methods and approaches exist to observe a certain parameter. For example, water turbidity can be measured by determining Secchi depth, using turbidity meters (nephelometers), total suspended solids, etc, or this can be estimated with regional-based EO algorithms. Physics-based numerical models, however, estimate the various components that contribute to the state of turbidity. It can therefore be hard to directly relate model input and output to field measurements.
- Lack of metadata may prevent the use of data as model input or for model validation. Examples include:

³ <https://doi.org/10.3390/books978-3-03943-065-9>

- Precise reporting of date and time of measurements, i.e. including information about time zone and/or summer/wintertime adjustments.
 - Information about the accuracy and precision of measurements.
 - Information about the measurement technique employed. Which measurement technique in field or methodology in laboratory was followed? What is the sensitivity of the measurement?
 - Lack of information about instrument calibration and maintenance. This information is useful for validating data sets prior to using them as input to models or using data for model validation. Sensor calibration and maintenance can explain instantaneous shifts in the observed values and the necessity of correcting or invalidating data, associated also to maintenance, change of equipment and calibration coefficients used, etc. One way to address this is to source datasets with already applied final quality control step.
- Particularly related to operational information and modelling, the data requirements are not clear to the community of *in-situ* observation scientists.

Interoperability of model data may be hampered by:

- Lack of a common approach to specify model accuracy and uncertainty.
- Absence of benchmarking exercises to compare different modelling tools or model outputs.
- Lack of sharing of best practices and approaches (modules).
- Lack of broad use of all available techniques to assimilate measured data in models (e.g. AI)

5.5. Example challenges related to the integration of different types of observation data

5.5.1. Case study for *in-situ* & low-cost observation integration

The use of low-cost sensors and measurement systems especially used by citizen scientists is supported and promoted by LandSeaLot and aims to increase the observational capabilities within the land-sea interface area. This has been shown in several milestones and deliverables in LandSeaLot (D4.1, D4.2, MS3, MS8). Such initiatives have been undertaken by other projects as well, and the recent Helmholtz Association funded Shaping Ocean of Possibilities project (SOOP) is a project with large geographic and thematic overlap with LandSeaLot, where measurement solutions using low-cost sensors are developed. In collaboration with LandSeaLot, some of the low-cost sensors listed in Table 2 in D4.2 were tested at the land sea interface within the Wadden Sea Rhine Elbe LIL. Additional tests are ongoing within LandSeaLot, for example within the Seine Estuary and Bay LIL, and the relevant results will be reported in the next deliverables. Based on these

tests, recommendations can be initiated for how low-cost sensors can be tested in LILs and evaluated in terms of accuracy, precision and proper handling.

Assuming that low-cost technology may be used in different domains along the LSI, it is important to consider sensors that can handle deployments in a gradient between freshwater and saltwater endmembers, and testing can help to determine low-cost sensor capabilities. In 2024 and 2025, Wadden Sea Rhine Elbe LIL researchers conducted a series of checks of sensors obtained from Atlas Scientific, within the SOOP project and after discussions with LandSeaLot WP4 colleagues, who have included these sensors as options for use with citizen science communities. These tests were done within deployment of these sensors in the SailingBox, i.e. a miniaturized flow-through measurement system for small boats and citizen science applications, developed in the SOOP project. The low-cost Atlas Scientific (New York, USA) sensors used in this development and listed in the WP4 low-cost sensor pool (LSL D4.1), were tested to assess their accuracy and precision (compared to conventional oceanographic sensors), as well as their durability. This is done in the following stepwise calibration and testing procedure, developed in 2004, and applied during 2024-2026 for temperature, conductivity, dissolved oxygen and pH:

1. Low-cost sensors (temperature, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, turbidity) were calibrated where applicable according to the manufacturer specifications.
2. Low-cost sensors were tested in the lab under controlled conditions, with a sample of natural water, next to high-precision sensors, specifically temperature, salinity, pH and dissolved oxygen. Presence of large deviations between expected and measured values were examined and sensors were recalibrated where necessary.
3. Low-cost sensors deployed in the SailingBox were placed at a coastal station, in the WSRE LIL, the Cuxhaven Research Station, alongside a FerryBox.
4. Low-cost sensor observations were compared to high-precision and accurate measurements from the FerryBox, and reproducibility, accuracy and precision was assessed.

Such low-cost sensor tests and calibrations are valuable to ensure proper integration and interoperability with available *in-situ* and EO observations at the LSI area, as well as operational models.

Hereafter the assessment of a conductivity sensor is included as an example variable, which used to calculate salinity, an essential parameter for investigating and characterizing observations at the LSI. A low-cost Atlas scientific sensor (New York, USA) within a SailingBox was deployed alongside high-precision SBE45 sensor (SeaBird, USA) within the FerryBox (4H-Jena Engineering, Germany) available at Cuxhaven Research station in the WSRE LIL. This station is located at the outflow of the Elbe Estuary into the North Sea and adjacent to the Wadden Sea, and experiences large gradients in temperature, salinity, pH, dissolved oxygen, as well as other biogeochemical parameters, driven by tidal dynamics

(Rewrie *et al.* 2025⁴). The gradients at such a station within the LSI area allow to test the sensor in natural, but also variable conditions over a short period of time (Figure 2), demonstrating high reliability of the low-cost sensor for observing conductivity with a slope of the regression line of 1, and a high R^2 value of close to 1. This record provides a reference, which can be associated with the low-cost sensor, when reporting the data and metadata from the low-cost sensor deployments and could be recommended for those researchers considering the use of similar low-cost sensors.

Following discussions within the LandSeaLot community involved in the deployment of low-cost sensor technologies, it was also suggested that such tests could be performed within larger EU initiatives and projects like the AQUARIUS Horizon Europe project. Here research infrastructure in the LSI area, and within for example the LILs in LSL is already in place, demonstrating a way for using available and EU funded research infrastructure, i.e. promote interoperability and efficient use of resources.

Figure 2: Comparison between conductivity observed with Atlas sensor (USA) deployed in a SailingBox (SB) and conductivity measured by high-precision Seabird SBE45 instrument within the FerryBox (FB). Both instruments were deployed at the Cuxhaven Research station within the SOOP project.

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2025.1548463>

6. Test cases from LILs

WP3 intends to use test cases to identify inter-comparison and harmonization opportunities across LILs, in terms of the current observation methods and standards, types of integration occurring etc. Test cases are defined as “an operational example of data integration occurring within a LIL.”

Each test case should be:

1. Relevant for a societal challenge within WP5 (though not all societal challenges have to be addressed).
2. Focussed on a small parameter set from the focus parameters (see preliminary results).
3. Cover a transferable workflow, and
4. Integrate *in-situ*, EO and model data.

The term ‘operational’ is used to indicate that these activities are already planned or ongoing in LandSeaLot WP5 and can be followed and assessed by WP3. WP3 aims to identify gaps, missing experiments to address those, similarities that allow LILs cooperation and support, as well as needs for training provided via WP6, etc.

LILs were requested to present possible test cases during the LandSeaLot week in January 2025 in Lisbon. Test cases across LILs were drafted from the LIL’s presentations to select the *in-situ* parameters (see preliminary results). These were, in most cases, refined by the Task 3.1 workgroup in consultation with LIL leads. Test cases are expected to also provide a range on meta data, e.g., methodologies, next to the data evaluation and integration workflow. WP5 has organized “thematic groups” (see Table 3) to streamline research within the LILs. Test cases will be matched to these “thematic groups” to facilitate the collaborative work between WP5 and WP3.

6.1. Integration activities to be tested in the LILs

Test cases conducted in the LILs will provide workflow examples for data integration. These will be developed for the identified priority parameters (see section 4.2) and then tested with and, where necessary, adjusted for other variables. The test cases address most societal challenges addressed by LandSeaLot (see Figure 1), including: Nutrients (3), Floods/extreme water levels (1), Heatwaves (1), and Carbon fluxes (4), Carbon budget (4), and Morphological evolution (1), but do not cover Biodiversity (0), Plastics (0), or Salt intrusion (0).

WP3 will continue to strongly interact with WP5 to assure the effective combination of test cases, thematic groups, priority parameters and coverage of societal challenges. This will also include interaction with WP6 where interoperability and standards are being discussed, output of (low-cost) sensors and citizen science will be improved in FAIRness (supporting integration), or training is required (especially in relation to low-cost sensors and river data). LILs are to provide draft workflows and GANTT charts for their respective

test case. For guidance, deadlines will be defined for: 1) for finalized test case workplans and 2) test case data integration workflows.

WP3 will collect further information from LILs with regards to how they currently collect *in-situ* data for the focus parameters (in addition to existing resources from D4.1 – “Summary of the technical and community needs of LILs” and D4.2). WP3 will oversee where test cases are conducting similar methodologies that can be tracked and analyzed.

Table 5: Test case studies per LandSeaLot Integration Lab (LIL) and relevant Priority Parameters and Thematic Groups.

LIL	Test case	Priority parameter ~ Thematic group
Baltic Sea	Combining/integrating CDOM from <i>in-situ</i> automated and manual observation with Earth Observation.	DOC/CDOM Carbon fluxes
Danube Delta	<i>In-situ</i> Chl data and reflectance with EO for Chl product	Chlorophyll / Nutrients
Firth of Forth	Integration of <i>in-situ</i> water level data with satellite radar data to calculate water level anomalies at the catchment level.	<i>In-situ</i> reflectance, Floods and sea water levels
North Aegean	Dissolve oxygen <i>in-situ</i> and modelling.	dissolved oxygen
Po Delta and North Adriatic	Use of <i>in-situ</i> DOC, CDOM (discrete samples) and FDOM (moored instrument) to assess DOC EO products (Test remote sensing algorithms for dissolved organic carbon pools in the North Adriatic).	DOC/CDOM, Carbon fluxes
Seine Estuary and Bay	Observing and anticipating sediment fluxes and morphodynamic changes in the LSI area: integrating SPM knowledge from <i>in-situ</i> observation, EO ocean colour measurements and model simulations.	Turbidity/SPM, Coastal erosion and estuarine morphodynamics
Tagus and Sado Estuaries System	Integration of water level and water temperature (derived from low-cost sensors and buoys) with EO products (e.g., CMEMS GLO/IBI L4) and numerical modelling (MOHID).	(water) temperature, Heatwaves

Wadden Sea,
Rhine Delta
and Elbe
Estuary

Integrating relationship of measured SPM to measured turbidity with model of SPM that influences productivity in the Elbe via light and nutrient availability

turbidity/SPM,
NO₃, Carbon fluxes,
Nutrients

Gulf of Lions,
Rhone Delta

Use of *in-situ* data (O₂, pH, temperature, salinity, etc.) with ANN and models for estimation of inorganic carbon.

(water) temperature,
dissolved oxygen,
Carbon fluxes

7. Recommendations for improved interoperability (protocols) and common observing systems (Preliminary results)

D3.1 identifies a set of common challenges concerning data availability, access and interoperability. While most different challenges were initially addressed for specific listed parameters, they are generally applicable for any *in-situ* observation along the LSI and are aggregated in Table 6.

Table 6: *In-situ* observation related challenges and recommended means of alleviation. The content was combined from workshop discussions and anonymous contributions to an open query table.

Challenge	category	recommendation
Sensor failure in HF data	gap	HF data missing data can be filled with gap-filling algorithms, this is not as suitable for sample measurements of low frequency, the success depends on the size of the gap
Already large providers/aggregators still do not have all the data, e.g., river water level in EMODnet	access	Leverage new products, e.g., SWOT for water level. Make use of, and assist, existing aggregators by contacting them and supplying data to them (e.g. https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/)
Data “pairs” for calibration need to be produced, do not readily exist, especially because they need to be location-specific	gap	Use/extend the use of quasi-autonomous platforms such as the FerryBox to overcome data gaps, and their communities (and link to EO)
Having to go to a website to get to the data for download	access	API access to FAIR data via computer programs instead of going to website, with filtering for good data using flags, e.g., “Coast HF” in France
Distributed data	access	[will be developed in future discussions]
Quality control, some available data cannot confidently be used as-is	interoperability	[will be developed in future discussions]
In-situ sample data are not always easy to integrate with high-frequency measurements	interoperability	[will be developed in future discussions]
comparing related parameters from different observing techniques, as techniques do not “see” the exact same signals: e.g., sample CHL vs fluorescence CHL; CDOM,	interoperability	Benchmark, correlate; have samples at the same time that satellite is passing; sample together with HF measurements; identify most suitable measurement of the target parameter, e.g., DOM absorption (especially in the

FDOM vs DOC sample measurements

blue) could be better than DOM fluorescence, but is harder to measure. Follow standards, also for metadata Agree on sampling depths

Gaps in low frequency measurements, e.g., SPM sample measurements for turbidity HF data

gap

[will be developed in future discussions]

Spatial gaps in HF observations

gap

Increase coverage by deploying more sensors, Explore gap filling methods using EO and model data

Observation data does not currently follow a standard format, especially for the cross-border water bodies

interoperability

common data standards [this is to be discussed in concert with work package 6: Data Management and services]

It is clear that “interoperability” is not well defined yet within the context of LandSeaLot and observations along the LSI. It is therefore recommended to find and agree upon one definition to be used within the project by the entire consortium.

The issues, especially of observation gaps in space and time, are somewhat system dependent. In some regions the LSI is well observed, while in others it is not.

For the Seine Estuary and Bay LIL, as an example, it was suggested that the use FerryBox technology on Voluntary Observing Ships is a recommendable addition to sampling on low frequency bases, such as done monthly for the MSFD. It was, however, noted that if one parameter is observed by different types of measurements, actions need to be taken to address challenges of interoperability.

For the Firth of Forth and Po Delta and North Adriatic LILs, it was discussed that *in-situ* measurements of organic carbon and fluxes of carbon should be complemented by additional data from EO. EO and HF measurements of carbon (proxies) may achieve better results if done on absorption rather than fluorescence of coloured organic matter. Calibrations and result validation via *in-situ* sample measurements are indispensable.

Table 7: Recommendations for addressing challenges in in-situ observations by observed parameter. This table was filled during and after the workshop and was available for input by all experts listed above.

recommendation	
general	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • API access to FAIR data via computer programs instead of going to website, with filtering for good data using flags; • “Coast HF” in France. HF data missing data can be filled with digital tools, this is not so suitable for sample measurements of low frequency, the success depends on the size of the gap; • Leverage new products, e.g. SWOT for water level; • Use/extend the use of quasi-autonomous platforms such as the FerryBox to overcome data gaps, and their communities (and link to EO). Make use of existing aggregators (e.g. https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/) by contacting them and supplying data to them
(water) temperature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More sensors, explore connections between EO and modellers experts
salinity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More sensors, explore connections between EO and modellers experts
dissolved oxygen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [no input]
turbidity/SPM/CHL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gaps in low frequency measurements. • Benchmark, have samples at the same time that satellite is passing - also better combination of (HF) <i>in-situ</i> observation with EO products. • Turbidity calibration from samples is also a key question/challenge
DOC/CDOM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calibrating CDOM (or FDOM) with DOC sample measurements, is location/region specific • Develop (regional) relationships between CDOM and salinity, i.e. proxies • DOM absorption (especially in the blue) could be better than DOM fluorescence, but is harder to measure; • Measure ocean colour spectra to find most suitable ones for interoperability between samples, HF and EO
Nutrients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [no input]
Water level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More sensors, explore connections between EO and modellers experts

8. Steps towards final report (D3.2, M34; lead: DELTARES)

In this Deliverable (D3.1) our approach was described to map and address inconsistencies, interoperability methods and alignment of observations and models. This approach will be employed to produce a final version of this Deliverable, i.e. D3.2.

8.1. Expert knowledge

To better understand the spatial gaps in *in-situ* observations within the European LSI, a map of observing infrastructures is planned. Experts were asked to supply relevant information (e.g., infrastructure location, observed parameters, observation frequencies) in a table in the online document and to use a second table to provide contact information for known observing structures/initiatives outside the LandSeaLot consortium. However, similar efforts have been made in other Research Infrastructures, e.g., in JERICO, and these will first be screened to produce an initial spatial map. WP4 will show which new cost-efficient sensors will be deployed in the different LILs, which will in turn indicate the existing needs of data gaps to be filled. WP6 will show the existing and shortly expected datasets used in the LILs, which will further inform the mapping of current and upcoming observations. The questionnaire addressing inconsistencies, interoperability methods and alignment of observations and models will be updated for wider European LSI researcher and practitioner communities, including those outside LandSeaLot. Following the collection of expert feedback, WP3 will be drafting recommendations for the interoperability of *in-situ* data and data from EO and models, and the integration of prerequisite parameters such as water level and bathymetry into the developing scheme. The recommended scheme will be tested in the LILs.

8.2. Common data repository for the Land Sea Interface area

Based on interaction with local stakeholders from the WP5 activities, the need was identified for a common data repository for the LSI area. Preferably, an already existing data repository should be used, and within the European scope of LandSeaLot, an EU based and funded one would be the first choice. Since this is an ambitious task, it will be approached iteratively, and LandSeaLot will only attempt to further investigate the possibilities for such a common data repository. The priority parameters will be addressed in relation to this. This effort is meant to identify what existing repositories can be used, such as CMEMS and EMODnet, to provide access specifically to LSI data. A common access repository will likely help overcome several of the issues of data inconsistencies, interoperability methods and alignment of observations and models.

8.3. Roadmap to Digital Twins at the LSI and applicability to LILs

The definition for a Digital Twin at the LSI area is critical for the development of the roadmap. Here LandSeaLot chooses to build on the architecture of a Digital Twin from the H2020 DOORS project, where the Physical world is connected to the Virtual world through a series of heterogeneous observations and platforms that include archived, near real time and real time data streams. These are coupled via a data centre to the engine of the Digital

Twin – that includes both numerical, data-based modelling components and Artificial Intelligence, that are coupled together to deliver dedicated services. Critical to the Digital Twin is the visualization and interactive front end, that also provide estimates of uncertainty and control to support the improvement of the asset performance and the real-world system being modelled.

Figure 3: High level overview of the architecture of a Digital Twin developed by the H2020 DOORS project, highlighting the key components to be considered in Task 3.4.

Whilst the ‘stepping stones’ for the start of the development of a Digital Twin are in place from some LILs, real challenges remain to realize their development and deployment. These include:

- **Data fusion and interoperability across many different data and observation platforms**, with different temporal and spatial resolutions, requiring harmonization and standardization, bridging observational domains and approaches, whilst taking account of sensor failure and data gaps
- **Coupling numerical models across the LSI area that are characterized by complex feedback mechanisms**, incorporating empirical models, whilst also ensuring two-way interaction with Modelled (virtual) and Observation (real) outputs to improve the Digital Twin and reduce uncertainty.
- **Architecture that couples heterogenous data streams with an ensemble of calibrated and validated model types** (numerical, empirical and Artificial Intelligence) and that enables two-way interaction, visualization and learning, minimizes computational burden, and focuses on specific challenges within the LSI area.

The roadmap (T3.4) will address these challenges, whilst also elaborating what are the minimum requirements for a Digital Twin at the land-sea interface.